

Proceedings of the
6th Brazilian Conference on Composite Materials

ISBN 978-65-00-49386-3

Part of ISSN 2316-1337

Organised & Edited by [R.J. da Silva](#) & [T.H. Panzera](#)

Content available at: doi.org/10.29327/566492

A preliminary investigation of fully water-immersed bio-based composites reinforced with short coir fibres

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Keywords: biobased polymer, coir short fibres, three-point bending, water saturation

Abstract: This work investigates the effects of water ageing on the three-point bending behaviour of composites made of castor oil polymer reinforced with short coir fibres treated in a 10% NaOH solution. A Design of Experiment (DoE) is performed to identify the effects of the factors (levels), fibre treatment (untreated and treated), and immersion exposure time (0, 8, and 16 days) on the flexural modulus and strength of the biobased composites. The exposure time significantly affects flexural modulus, while both factors affect flexural strength. Higher exposure times and fibre treatment lead to lower mechanical properties attributed to the easier percolation of water by the excessive lignin removal.

Fundings: CAPES MSc scholarship (#88887.488889/2020-00) and CNPq (PQ 309885/2019-1).

1. Introduction

The consumption of plastic products over the years has generated a large number of wastes which accumulate in landfills, causing considerable environmental problems [1]. Non-biodegradable plastics or polymers contribute significantly to these problems, as they have high resistance to degradation, taking years to decompose. Therefore, researchers and industry have been looking for alternatives to minimise the environmental impacts caused by the improper disposal of products made from plastics [2]. The use of biodegradable polymers is an ecological alternative to reduce the environmental impacts. Among the biodegradable polymers, the ones that have attracted the most attention are those obtained from renewable sources due to their lower environmental impact.

Tiradentes, Minas Gerais, Brazil

14-18th August 2022

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Castor bean is an abundant plant in Brazil, and its use can be relatively simple. Castor oil represents a promising raw material due to its low cost, low toxicity, and availability as a renewable agricultural resource. Coir fibres are obtained from the coconut husk and correspond to about 30% of the fruit. Coconut husk is a lignocellulosic material corresponding to 80-85% of the fruit's weight. Coir fibres are highly lignified, and their chemical composition varies according to weather conditions and fruit maturation. Coir fibre has a relative advantage in abundance and cost, as Brazil is a major worldwide consumer of green coconut [3].

The effect of moisture ageing on epoxy and flax fibre composites was reported [4]. Samples were placed in climatic chambers with humidity of 50% and 21°C, and remained in saturation for 2, 4, 8 and 16 days. Other samples were immersed in water and kept in saturation for 2, 4 and 8 days. The results showed that water absorption increases progressively with ageing time, compromising the flexural properties of the composites. Furthermore, the loss in flexural properties occurs much faster in a fully saturated environment.

The ageing caused by water and alkaline solutions in epoxy composites reinforced with jute and basalt fibres was investigated [5]. The jute fibres underwent alkaline treatment in NaOH with a concentration of 5% for 30 minutes. Another group of samples underwent treatment with silane, with a concentration of 3% for 2 hours. Jute fibre composites made with (i) untreated fibres, (ii) treated with NaOH and (iii) treated with silane; and basalt fibre composites made with untreated fibres were evaluated in four different ageing conditions: 180 days underwater at 20°C and 40°C, and under alkaline solution at 20°C and 40°C. The results showed that the jute composites gained more weight than the basalt ones and that the treatments reduced water absorption, increasing the tensile strength of the composites.

This work investigates the effects of water saturation on the three-point bending behaviour of coir fibre composites composed of a castor oil biobased matrix phase. Short coir fibres, randomly arranged, are treated in a 10% NaOH solution for short periods (up to 8 hours). The flexural modulus and strength (ASTM D790 [6]) are evaluated considering the factors (levels): fibre treatment (untreated and treated) and exposure time (0, 8, and 16 days).

2. Methodology

2.1. Fibre characterisation

The natural fibres were previously treated with NaOH solution in 10% concentration for 1, 2, 4 and 8 hours, as reported by [7]. After treatment, all conditions are exposed to 55% relative humidity for ten days. Subsequently, the fibres are tested in tension using an Instron® testing machine equipped with a 50 kN load cell (Figure 1 A).

According to ASTM D3822 [8], at 2 mm/min, five different conditions are tested without treatment and four treated conditions. The fibre diameters are measured using a Scanning Electron Microscopy (Figure 1 B) and the ImageJ software. Forty (40) samples are considered to obtain mean tensile strength and modulus.

2.2. Composites fabrication

The composite plates (280 x 280 x 3.5 mm³) are fabricated by cold pressing and randomly arranged castor resin matrix and short coir fibres. A constant fibre mass fraction of 30% is considered, as reported by [9].

The untreated and treated fibres that achieved the best results from the tensile test of individual fibres are used to fabricate the composite plates. The curing process considers 15 days at 21°C and constant humidity at approximately 55%. Subsequently, the composites are fully immersed in water for 8 or 16 days.

2.3. Composites characterisation

The three-point bending tests are performed according to ASTM D790 (Figure 2) to obtain the flexural modulus and strength of the composites. Ten (10) samples (65 x 13 x 3.5 mm³) and one replica per condition are tested using a Shimadzu® testing machine with a 100 kN load cell at 2 mm/min and 60 mm span length.

Fig. 1. Tensile test of individual fibres (A) and fibre diameter measurement by SEM (B).

Fig. 2. Three-point bending.

3. Results and Discussions

The histograms for the probability distribution of the elastic modulus and tensile strength of the fibres are shown in Figure 3. The treatment lasting 8 hours proved to be more effective in improving the mechanical performance of the fibres, being chosen for the manufacture of composites. Alkaline treatment can remove part of the lignin leading to a reorientation of the microfibril angles, with consequent mechanical improvement [4].

Fig. 3. Histograms for the probability distribution of the elastic modulus and tensile strength of the fibres.

Figure 4 shows the mean stress-strain curves obtained for the composite (16 days exposure time) under three-point bending and a typical sample fracture image. A full-fibre rupture is evidenced on the bottom side of the beam under tensile stresses.

Fig. 4. Mean stress-strain curves for treated and untreated fibre composites (16 days exposure time).

Table 1 shows the DoE model data. The main factors or their interactions are only analysed if they are significant with 95% confidence (P-value ≤ 0.05 , highlighted in bold). Exposure time significantly affects the flexural modulus, while strength is affected by both factors. Interaction effects are not significant as P-values are greater than 0.05.

Table 1. DoE model analysis.

Assumptions under verification: residuals are normally distributed and have equal variances.		
	Flexural Modulus	Flexural Strength
R ²	86.01%	89.35%
R ² (adj)	74.35%	80.47%
P-Value ^{AD (RESI)}	0.225	0.179
P-Value ^{B (RESI)}	0.746	0.702
P-Value ^{Treatment}	0.116	0.011
P-Value ^{Exposure}	0.004	0.003
P-Value ^{int}	0.521	0.867

R² determine how well the model fits the data; R² (adj) is the percentage of the variation in the responses that is explained by the model; P-Value^{AD (RESI)} is the Anderson Darling test of residuals and values greater than 0.05 indicate normal distribution; P-Value^{B (RESI)} is the Barlett’s test of residuals and values greater than 0.05 indicate homogeneity of variances; P-Value^{Treatment}, P-Value^{Exposure} and P-Value^{int} indicate, respectively, if the treatment of fibres, the exposure time and the interaction of factors influence responses, and values lesser than 0.05 indicate significant influence.

Figure 5 shows the main effect plot for exposure time for the adjusted means of flexural modulus, which varies from 0.23 to 0.49 MPa. The immersion exposure time substantially reduces the composite stiffness (up to 53.06%). The percolation of water inside the composite can hinder the interfacial bonding condition, especially due to the natural fibre swelling [4, 5].

Figure 6 shows the main effect plots for the adjusted means of flexural strength, which varies from 5.84 to 13.58 MPa. Composites made with treated fibres lead to reduced flexural strength (35.17%), as well as the exposure time with a substantial drop up to 57.00%. This behaviour can be attributed to the excessive removal of lignin by the alkaline treatment, facilitating the percolation of water, especially when considering a long time of exposure. The microstructural analysis will be the scope of future investigations to understand such mechanisms better.

Fig. 5. Main effect plot for flexural modulus.

Fig. 6. Main effect plots for flexural strength.

4. Conclusions

The effects of fully water-immersed ageing on the flexural properties of coir fibre composites composed of biobased polymer were investigated using a statistical design. Flexural modulus was affected by immersion time, while strength was affected by immersion exposure time and fibre treatment. Although the fibre treatment increased the tensile properties of the fibre, the same trend was not evidenced when incorporated into the composite material. Reductions in flexural stiffness and strength were observed due to increased exposure time, mainly for treated fibres, attributed to excessive lignin degradation and faster water percolation, which might have compromised the interface condition. Further microstructural analysis will perform for better understanding such mechanisms.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Credit author statement

E.G. Assis: Methodology; Investigation; Data curation; Writing – original draft. **R.J. da Silva:** Methodology; Formal analysis; Writing – original draft. **J.C. dos Santos:** Investigation. **A.L. Christoforo:** Methodology. **T.H. Panzera:** Conceptualisation; Methodology; Resources; Supervision; Writing – review.

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